
Study on the International Communication Paths of Jingchu ICH Cultural and Creative Products Represented by Jingzhou Folk Embroidery

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Abstract:

(ICH) within the scenario of the alignment development between the Cultural Power Strategy and "Belt and Road", innovating ICH creative products as key vehicles for the global circulation of intangible cultural heritages deserves extensive efforts to improve China's international cultural influence. Jingzhou folk embroidery is taken as an exemplary case for this research project. The current study delves into Jingzhou folk embroidery by mainly observing the situation and problems of its present international communication process, and points out its shortcomings in several aspects like limited content, low degree of digitalization, and lack of human resources. A lot of advice is given through consultation with experts from various aspects under the context of cultural inheritance and modern communication rules, aiming at those three improvement directions about optimizing communication approaches to highlight the character of Jingzhou folk embroidery: First, making use of traditional culture as resources for innovation by adding modern elements to products; second, using bilingual short videos and Amazon cross-border e-commerce as two forms of tools to create a digital communication system of creativity; third, striving for communication opportunities by making good use of policies. This research study provides a concrete path for the international development of Jingzhou folk embroidery, while providing an exemplary line of thinking of communication opportunities for the international communication way of other regional ICH creative products. In so doing, Jingzhou folk embroidery plays a role in supporting the domestic strategic deployment of promoting ICH going global.

Keywords: Jingzhou folk embroidery; intangible cultural heritage (ICH); international communication; strategies

Against the backdrop of increasing globalization and in-depth exchanges between civilizations, the international dissemination of intangible cultural heritage (ICH) has become a crucial element in building a country's cultural soft power. China has been vigorously advancing the cultural power strategy and the Belt and Road Initiative, making the global promotion of fine traditional Chinese culture a prominent topic of discussion. As an integral component of Chinese civilization, Jingchu culture, boasting profound historical heritage and unique aesthetic value, possesses distinctive advantages as a medium for narrating Chinese stories to the world. Jingzhou folk embroidery, which integrates the essence of Jingchu cultural craftsmanship with cultural symbols, stands out as a

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representative carrier for cultural communication among Jingchu's ICH items.

Despite the remarkable achievements made in platform construction and promotion for the international dissemination of China's ICH, high-context and regionally distinctive ICH projects such as Jingzhou folk embroidery still confront prevalent challenges, including obstacles in the modern interpretation of traditional culture, high cross-border cognitive barriers, and a lack of sustainable promotion models.^[1]

In light of the aforementioned context, this study takes Jingzhou folk embroidery as a case study to conduct an in-depth analysis of the practical problems encountered by its cultural and creative products in the process of international dissemination, as well as their feasible development paths.^[2] Starting from the strategic and resource perspectives, the paper examines the current status of dissemination and existing bottlenecks. Furthermore, it proposes systematic optimization strategies from three dimensions—product innovation, digital communication, and policy support—to facilitate the internationalization of such ICH projects and promote the smoother integration of Chinese culture into the global arena.^[3]

I.The Context for Global Promotion of Cultural & Creative Products Originated from Jingchu's Intangible Cultural Heritage(Jingchu: Jingzhou City – in Hubei Province)

(ICH)in light of the new era trend of the intertwining of globalization and digitalization, the changes that have occurred in cultural communication not only reflects on the level of importance to national soft power competition,^[4] but also shows it is an important channel for conducting exchanges and conducting international cooperation. As one element of fine traditional Chinese culture, Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) in Jingchu region is responsible for conveying the unique cultural attributes of the region's culture and intensifying cultural confidence through its international transmission of creative products, making it an effective means by which to implement national cultural policies and participate in global cultural governance.^[5] When exploring the process of its international transmission, a comprehensive research can be done through exploring strategy, resources, and technology to provide a solid basis for elucidating the significance, possibility, and future development path of Jingchu's ICH transcending the borders.^[6]

(I) Strategic Dimension: The Core Driving Force for Building a Cultural Power

(ICH)the Fourteenth Five-Year Plan for National Economic and Social Development and Outline of Long-Term Goals for 2035 as well as Opinions on Fully Implementing Projects for the Inheritance and Development of Fine Traditional Chinese Culture emphasize the need to foster cultural confidence and make it a driving force in national rejuvenation.^[7] Fine traditional Chinese culture, is the crystallization of the national spirit, and the basic means of national development, which serves as an important path for inheriting and innovating ICH such as Jingchu embroidery and thus promoting cultural power; ICH represents a living symbol of the continuous culture of China.^[8] Use citation for the following statement: the 14th Five-Year Plan for National Development and the Opinions on Implementing the Project for the Inheritance and Development of Fine Traditional Chinese Culture.^[9]

With the steady and in-depth advancement of the Belt and Road Initiative, Jingchu embroidery, as an

integral component of fine traditional Chinese culture, has ushered in new opportunities for global dissemination.^[10] It is imperative to anchor ourselves in the spiritual essence of Chu culture, comprehensively and systematically explore, collate, and innovate the artistic language and expressive content of Jingchu embroidery, and establish a diversified and collaborative international communication system featuring diverse channels and modern discourse.^[11] By doing so, we can facilitate the creative transformation of this time-honored treasure from a regional handicraft into a global cultural resource.^[9] This constitutes a proactive practical endeavor to uphold cultural confidence and fully showcase the charm of Chinese culture.^[12]

It acts as a way of imparting such shared universal human values to the world through intercivilizational exchanges so that they can contribute to building a firm foundation for global public opinion and cultural identity to support cultural powers.^[13]

(II) Resource Dimension: The Unique Endowments of Chu Culture

As the core birthplace of Chu culture and the political center during its heyday, Jingzhou served as the capital for twenty generations of Chu kings, accumulating profound historical heritage and cultural genes.^[14] The city is home to numerous Chu tomb sites. A notable example is Mashan Tomb No. 1, excavated archaeologically in 1982, which is hailed as the "Treasure Trove of Warring States Silk Fabrics."^[15] The embroidered works, brocades, and costumes unearthed therefrom collectively embody the romantic, vivid, mysterious, and magnificent aesthetic style of Chu culture in terms of material, patterns, and craftsmanship. These relics reflect the Chu people's worldview of "harmony between humans and nature" and their ritual tradition of "harmony between gods and humans."

Immersed in such a rich Chu cultural milieu, Jingzhou folk embroidery has, with the passage of history, absorbed a wide range of elements and gradually evolved into a pivotal carrier for inheriting the essence of Chu culture. Most of its patterns revolve around themes such as phoenixes, dragons and tigers, as well as trailing grasses and flowing clouds.^[16] Characterized by full and unrestrained compositions, rich colors with striking contrasts, the embroidery fully exhibits the distinctive vitality and dynamism as well as the mystical and enchanting aura inherent in Chu art. Meanwhile, it incorporates profound philosophical connotations such as "revering heaven and ancestors" and "balancing virtue and punishment." Boasting exquisite and diverse stitching techniques along with masterful craftsmanship, Jingzhou folk embroidery has transcended the scope of mere practical functions, evolving into a unique artistic form that integrates historical, aesthetic, and ideological values.^[17]

(III) Technical Dimension: The Internet as a Global Link

(ICH)continuous evolution and progress of Internet technologies have created numerous channels through which ICH can spread and flourish, extending both the geographical areas in which its practices reach people and the effectiveness of such efforts. For one thing, the development of Internet technologies has offered favorable conditions to ICH dissemination from various angles, mainly in the following three ways.

Cross-border e-commerce platforms and social media can even obliterate the boundaries between

countries. Products of ICH can be sold in the world by users from foreign countries. An example is when Hubei Tour's second leg of its "Walking with Hui" visit went to Jingzhou on March 24, 2024. Dong Yuhui and company promoted Jingzhou's culture and local specialities by playing different contents, namely a tour guide, livestreaming travel experience, and promotion of local specialties at the same time. The viewers exceeded more than 100,000 and people clicked on like for 130 million times during the livestream.

Technologies such as Augmented Reality (AR) and 3D modeling have greatly enriched the ways of cultural perception. The Jingzhou King Chu's Chariot and Horse Array Scenic Area has achieved innovative breakthroughs in traditional cultural exhibition models through the "Technology - Empowered Initiative for Building Chu Culture IP". It has leveraged technological means to bring cultural relics "to life", creating a new touchable, participatory and communicable platform for social science popularization. Insights into international preferences derived from big data analysis facilitate targeted innovation of ICH products, promoting the in-depth integration of cultural export and market adaptation.^[18]

It is obvious that internet sets up a bridge among technology, channels and users, facilitating the transformation of ICH from traditional craftsmanship to consumer products, and allowing these ICH products to reach consumers across the world.^[19]

II. Problems in the International Communication of Jingzhou Folk Embroidery

Currently, China has made certain breakthroughs in the international communication of ICH in terms of the diversification of subjects, the expansion of audiences, the broadening of content, and the diversification of forms. However, there are many in-depth problems. Especially under the current background of building a culturally powerful country, the goal of "transforming the civilian-oriented narration of elite culture and the popular expression of regional culture"—promoting the distinctive lifestyles of the small, high-context "cultural fans" groups to mass media platforms, and enabling more ordinary people to see the most authentic and original aspects through the transformation of communication strategies and expression styles, as well as understanding the most distinctive and regionally unique cultural content of a place by cognizing the world across borders in digital form, so as to make it a tangible "perceivable and touchable" carrier of civilization in the true sense and ultimately promote the internationalization of Chinese culture – has not yet been fully achieved. At this stage, the problems in this communication mainly include three aspects: first, insufficient depth and breadth; second, insufficient digitalization level; third, shortage of human resources.^[20]

(I) Lack of Depth and Breadth in Communication Content

The international communication of Jingzhou Folk Embroidery remains at a superficial, simplistic, and symbolic level. Various traditional elements are merely piled up without in-depth exploration at the spiritual level, ignoring the profound connotations and long-standing cultural heritage behind Jingzhou Folk Embroidery, which leads to biased information transmission. Due to the lack of relevant cultural and creative products that describe the rich implications of the local ICH culture in its specific context, many international audiences find it difficult to understand the in-depth connotations and spiritual essence of this local ICH culture to a certain extent.^[21] The patterns of Jingchu Embroidery (such as the

dragon patterns, phoenix patterns, panchi patterns, as well as the unique cloud patterns and scroll grass patterns mentioned in Chu culture) embody profound, mysterious, and romantic feelings, as well as folk customs and cultural meanings. However, these are relatively difficult for many foreign consumers to understand. Moreover, the inheritance method of Jingchu Embroidery is inherited from Chu Embroidery. Therefore, how to preserve the core techniques of this traditional cultural “intangible heritage” of Jingchu Embroidery, realize its “creative transformation” and “innovative development”, and avoid undermining its own cultural taste through blind replication, simple splicing of identical models, and low-cost production has become a key issue.

(II) Insufficient Level of Digital Communication

Under the new situation, with the rapid development of digital information technologies represented by big data, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence (AI), communication has entered a new stage of upgrading and iteration, showing a trend of continuous evolution of communication methods and frequent updates of communication platforms. However, in the presentation of Jingzhou Folk Embroidery’s cultural and creative products, the application of digital technology is still lacking, and there is a failure to achieve good adaptation with some important new media platforms. Additionally, the promotion, publicity, and communication methods of some Jingzhou Folk Embroidery cultural and creative products remain relatively traditional, and the construction and application of communication channels lack systematization. Most of the communication relies on simple short videos and offline museums. There is a lack of digital means and highly interactive designs to empower the digital display of Jingzhou Folk Embroidery cultural and creative products and present them to international audiences, especially in terms of highlighting the sense of mystery and decorative features of Jingchu culture. As a result, its cultural communication fails to meet the needs of current international audiences. At present, the traditional display method does not provide an immersive experience for international friends, making it difficult to showcase the ICH art of Jingzhou Folk Embroidery. For example, various international cultural exchange activities mainly involve foreign friends visiting cultural and creative exhibits related to Jingzhou Folk Embroidery (such as clothing and scarves) and watching performances related to Jingzhou Folk Embroidery in China. These communication methods lack a sense of participation, making it impossible for international friends to fully understand the connotations and values of this ICH, which greatly reduces the effectiveness of cultural communication. Similarly, the production of high-quality digital content based on VR, AR, and other technologies usually requires professional teams and substantial financial support.^[22] However, due to the constraints of Jingzhou’s economic conditions and industrial scale, many aspects fail to meet the requirements of international communication and telling Chinese stories well to the world.^[23]

(III) Dual Dilemmas of Talents and Resources

Before the research, the research team visited the exhibition hall of Ms. Wang Xuanzhen, an inheritor of the local ICH project of folk embroidery in Jingzhou. It was learned that the inheritance of Jingzhou Folk Embroidery is currently facing the problems of high time costs and lack of financial support, which have greatly hindered its international development. Learning the ICH embroidery techniques is highly difficult and requires a large amount of time and energy for long-term immersive practice to become a master craftsman. Taking traditional embroidery as an example, it takes at least several years and even decades to move from learning a certain stitching method to proficient application and

creating excellent works. In today's rapidly developing society with a fast-paced lifestyle, most young people are reluctant to make such attempts, worrying that they may not achieve the desired results, leading to a waste of time and resources, and thus considering the investment in ICH techniques as not worthwhile. In addition, there is very little financial support for the inheritance of this folk embroidery technique. The protection, inheritance, and development of Jingzhou Folk Embroidery require a large amount of funds, but there is no stable and sufficient financial support. Currently, it mainly relies on government financial investment and a small amount of social capital injection, lacking stable channels for capital inflow. Therefore, the problem of insufficient funds leads to many practical difficulties in the inheritance of Jingzhou Folk Embroidery. It cannot provide sufficient economic income support for the inheritors, which affects their enthusiasm. Inheritors may even abandon the craft, resulting in the loss of inheritors.

Furthermore, the lack of talent teams with international perspectives and communication technologies has seriously affected the development of international communication work in medium and small-sized cities like Jingzhou. Under the existing structure, the international communication of local cities is still undertaken by local official media.^[24] However, for a long time, local media have mainly been responsible for reporting domestic news, especially local political and people's livelihood news. In the process of conducting international communication, they face problems such as unclear sense of mission, limited theoretical level and technical capabilities, and fear of difficulties, making it difficult for them to adapt to the new international communication pattern.^[25]

III. International Communication Strategies for Jingzhou Folk Embroidery Creative Products

To address the aforementioned challenges in international communication, Jingzhou folk embroidery creative products have formulated corresponding international communication paths. It is hoped that in the era of advanced digital media technology, this study can provide a valuable reference for Jingzhou folk embroidery culture to go global. Therefore, three main international communication paths are proposed: innovative integration, digital communication, and policy empowerment.^{[26][27]}

(I) Innovative Integration: The Symbiotic Path of Traditional Culture and Modern Design

Jingzhou folk embroidery embodies more than 2,000 years of Chu cultural genes^[28], with its historical roots deeply embedded in the tradition of Chu embroidery. It shines worldwide with unique regional symbols, among which the phoenix patterns and coiled dragon patterns—symbolizing the spirit of the Chu people—are particularly prominent^[28]. Complemented by flowing geometric patterns and scroll grass patterns, the interwoven lines exude a romantic sense of dynamism. The essence of this embroidery craft lies in "single stitches interlocking and double stitches braiding," which can present rich colors and smooth surfaces on silk^[29]. Its color system is based on warm tones, skillfully using three to five high-contrast color blocks to create a magnificent and vivid atmosphere through lightness contrast^[30]. The patterns carry cultural connotations of praying for blessings and identifying status, reflecting the romantic temperament and profound aesthetic value of Chu culture, thus becoming a precious intangible cultural heritage.

Figure 1: Works by Wang Xuanzhen, an inheritor of the intangible cultural heritage of Jingzhou folk embroidery

Modern design takes human needs as its core, emphasizes function, user experience, simple style, sustainable nature, and brand story. Internationally speaking, the trend of minimalist, transcultural fusion development is prevailing, bridging technology integration and personal expression as bridges of past and present, domestic and foreign.

In their symbiosis, rather than being spliced or replaced, they require people to understand the cultural foundations and essential spiritual signifiers manifested through regional motifs^[31], materials, colors, techniques, including Chu embroidery patterns and distinctive shapes of the unearthed works; using modern methods to convert them into an updated expression using contemporary aesthetics and material for a more universal audience and usage in today's world. Besides, exploring material innovation, technical incorporation, form expansion and improved techniques to make them complement each other: modern design igniting the vigor within traditions while traditional forms offer enriched elements to modern designs so that these may reach an international consensus.^[32]

It is a must now. In response to such intricate challenges encountered by traditional handicrafts as shrinking domestic market, broken heritage transmission, gap between generational aesthetics, difficulty in international communication, these problems come along with different aspects of cultural barriers, lack of functionality and modernity,^{[33][34]} etc. They fail to adapt to consumers' changing requirements, are hard to sell overseas, while modern design helps them bring high quality to their products so that they can be more appropriate in daily use and well received across borders. All these were embodied in Jingzhou embroidery, which bears abundant visual symbols and has distinctive color and exquisite handwork. Chinese designer Sori Yanagi adapted Western functionalism into traditional Japanese aesthetics and created works with both national style and modernity, proving that the core principle of modern design is to base on the traditional beauty values to design for the lifestyles of the present day

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mankind, leading the way of modern design's global expansion.

Figure 2: Representative Design Works by Sori Yanagi

The specific pathway for integration requires advancement from various perspectives. Firstly, the extraction and recreation of pattern elements need further advance.^[35] Take the typical patterns such as phoenix and coiled dragon as examples, we should reveal the inherent spiritual connotations and express them innovatively with modern technology like geometrical abstractions, line simplifications and deconstructive reorganization; secondly, reconstructing iconic block colors to adapt to international aesthetics. Secondly, improve craftsmanship and conduct cross-border applications. Upholding the intrinsic content of core handcraft techniques, actively explore material innovation and tool optimization, gradually perfect the innovation concepts in handcraft processing work, transform through the following forms such as integrating the handcraft technique of embroidery into the digital print, 3D printing and using it on the interior decoration of buildings or the installation of digital art. The team led by Wang Xuanzhen, an inheritor of Jingzhou folk embroidery, remade, from scale, the "Phoenix and Dragon Pattern" embroidered robe retrieved from the Mashan Chu Tomb^[36], and made an incorporeal moxa sachet by weaving together the intangible cultural heritage of Jiaoai, and the team won gold in the Hubei tourism competition in 2025, and through cross-border e-commerce sold to Japan, South Korea, and Southeast Asia with more than 800 thousand sets a year.

The form and function of products are transforming towards modernization, breaking the limitation of traditional embroidery being merely decorations and clothing accessories. The unique aesthetic elements of embroidery are integrated into a wider range of modern life scenarios, developing cultural and creative products that are functional, practical, and portable—such as electronic device cases, eco-friendly tote bags, travel storage items^[37], and business office accessories integrated with Chu patterns. For example, the Jingzhou Museum collaborated with young inheritor Li Chenting to transform the cultural relic pattern of the "Tiger-shaped Bird Stand Drum" in its collection into the high-end minimalist hair accessory series Phoenix Perching-Chu Embroidery, which won the Silver Award at the "Phoenix Arrives, Jingzhou Presents Gifts" Design Competition. This successfully promoted the Chu culture IP from exhibition cabinets to daily life scenarios.

The narrative methods and brand building are moving towards modernization, constructing a complete

and clear modern brand visual identity system. It conveys the various cultural stories embodied in Jingzhou embroidery through an international narrative approach—such as the romantic spirit of the Chu people and the artistic connotation of the phoenix—and integrates all these into a simple, direct story that is understandable and resonant to people around the world. It strives to present the warmth of handcraft, the cultural connotation, and the uniqueness of the craftsmen's inheritance, enriching the product's value from another dimension and enhancing its added value and brand recognition. In August 2025, as part of the "Silk Road Aesthetics" project, Jingzhou Chu embroidery made its debut at CCTV's Splendid Clothing Under the Sky Silk Road Fashion Show.^[38] Led by international supermodel You Tianyi, the show featured Chu embroidery pouches and silk scarves, completing the modern transformation and cultural export of traditional symbols under the model of "intangible cultural heritage + fashion + international communication".

(II) Digital Communication: Bilingual Short Videos and Systematic Operation of Overseas Accounts

To achieve the global dissemination of intangible cultural heritage (ICH), it is necessary not only to conduct in-depth development and exploration of Jingzhou embroidery and other ICH items but also to fully utilize short videos to create three-dimensional and immersive communication scenarios.^[39] Additionally, in the integration of the digital economy and cultural communication, cross-border e-commerce platforms should be effectively used for precise market docking and commercial operations, realizing the transformation of ICH cultural symbols into daily and commercially valuable products—this is also a tough challenge in the international communication of Jingzhou folk embroidery.

1. New Media: The Core Communication Engine to Break Cultural Barriers

The 54th Statistical Report on Internet Development in China shows that as of June 2024, the number of short video users in China reached 1.05 billion, with a penetration rate of 95.5% among netizens. Short video platforms have become important information dissemination channels in China. In 2023, there were 1,428 ICH inheritors on Douyin, including 199 under the age of 30, and video content created by young ICH creators under 30 has gained increasing popularity. For example, Wang Shi, a post-2000s inheritor of Wang's Shadow Puppetry in Shaanxi, used shadow puppets to interpret characters like Michael Jackson and Optimus Prime through short videos.^[40] Lang Jiaziyu, a post-1990s third-generation inheritor of "Noodle Man Lang", "restored Hayao Miyazaki's animations and Bing Dwen Dwen with dough sculpture. Works by young inheritors combine ICH craftsmanship with social attention, frequently becoming viral hits. Today, a large number of users publish, watch, and disseminate ICH short videos through short video platforms. According to the 2023 ICH Data Report released by Douyin, as of May 2023, there were an average of 19,000 ICH live broadcasts per day and 13 ICH content broadcasts per minute on the platform. Furthermore, Bilibili's Annual Guofeng (Chinese-style) Data Report shows that the number of Guofeng enthusiasts on Bilibili exceeded 177 million, who are mainly interested in content such as traditional musical instruments, opera singing, and ICH crafts. Thus, short videos have become a major promotional tool for ICH today.

Short videos offer high-definition lenses, macro photography and slow-motion recording methods to

display the minute details of ICH workmanship to an audience, allowing viewers to fully feel the value of this labour-demanding job. Douyin blogger Shan Bai shot a series of macro photography showcasing the complete process of creating Xiangxi paper umbrellas and Han paper, allowing the audience to feel the scarcity of their creation of ICH artworks.^[41] In the meantime, the full-screen effect of short video gives audience an immersive feeling. And also ignites people's passion for protecting and inheriting ICH crafts. Besides, these video clips utilize story-telling technique (such as "master-apprentice inheritance", "craftsmen's dedication") to give people such ICH more narrations and humanistic touch which makes traditional culture more accessible to youth and reduce the gap between themselves and first-class traditional Chinese culture.

In addition, promotion should be carried out on overseas platforms such as TikTok and YouTube in conjunction with the launch time of products and current hot topics. For example, when the 2025 film *Ne Zha 2* topped the box office, cute *Ne Zha* images could be created based on the popular characters from the film on Douyin. This not only allows netizens to appreciate the exquisite craftsmanship of Jingzhou folk embroidery while watching the videos but also breaks through circles, shortens distances, helps more people understand the charm of ICH, and shatters the stereotype that traditional ICH is "rigid and outdated." Moreover, increasing the frequency of short video releases can extend interaction with users. Bilingual post-edited short videos are more likely to attract the attention of foreign netizens, thereby promoting Jingzhou folk embroidery cultural and creative products overseas.^[42]

2. Cross-border E-commerce: Building a Global Commercial Closed Loop for ICH Creative Products

Founded in 1999, Amazon has now become one of the world's second-largest e-commerce platforms.^[43] Amazon stores offer a variety of services to sellers, helping them improve performance and profitability, while providing buyers with a wider range of product categories and a better shopping experience. Amazon's product range covers books, home appliances, clothing, beauty, food, and other categories. With advantages such as a large user base, globalization,^[45] a safe and high-quality trading platform, and powerful sales and shipping tools, Amazon and other influential global e-commerce platforms should be fully utilized in the global sales of ICH creative products.^[44] Platform advantages should be leveraged to amplify product influence, and sufficient preliminary research should be conducted to meet market demand, innovate and upgrade creative products in a timely manner, and provide high-quality, accessible products to the public.

Amazon's rich functional modules can be used to accurately match the characteristics of embroidery products: Firstly, the refined classification function can be used to accurately categorize embroidery creative products into vertical categories such as "handicrafts," "folk culture derivatives," and "high-end home decorations," making it easier for target customers to search by keywords. Secondly, the platform provides a data analysis module (Amazon Analytics), which can real-time monitor search frequency, purchase frequency, and hot review keywords among people in different regions. This provides a basis for the operation team to adjust marketing activities in real time. For example, if data feedback shows that Europeans prefer smaller and more portable embroidery products, more diverse items such as cuffs and bookmarks can be developed based on existing small accessories. If data indicates that North American consumers like collecting home decoration products, new categories such as embroidered tapestries and cushions can be launched to complement the existing product line.

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Continuous feedback from consumers on the platform should be listened to, incorporated into works in a timely manner, and products should be continuously improved.^[46]

(III) Policy Empowerment: Government Support for the International Communication of Jingzhou Embroidery

1. Integrate National Platforms and High-end Diplomatic Resources to Create an International Business Card for Jingzhou Embroidery

In order for the strategy target of Jingzhou's international communication of folk embroidery to be realized, the government needs to rationally utilize the current existing policy resource allocation, provide specific and powerful policy support for some key links and areas, and establish an international communication platform as the core focus on building the global market and establishing a cultural brand, targeting the particular policy support mentioned above. The effective method used here could learn from the successful experience of hosting the Chu Culture Festival and the cooperation between the Big Data Festival of the China Movie Channel and the City of Jingzhou, to immediately boost the city's visibility and a higher level cultural brand through outstanding high-quality events.

Specifically, a special support mechanism should be established in key national foreign cultural trade platforms, such as the China International Fair for Trade in Services and the Shenzhen Cultural Industry Fair.^[47] Jingzhou embroidery should be prioritized for inclusion in the exhibition area of the National Cultural Export Base with targeted support, including subsidies for booth fees, as well as supporting professional translation and cross-border marketing services to reduce the difficulty for small and medium-sized enterprises to expand overseas. In addition, in urban foreign publicity, the level of communication should be elevated through high-level diplomatic activities. Systematic planning should be carried out to incorporate Jingzhou embroidery-themed exhibitions and ICH experience workshops under frameworks such as the "China Cultural Year," "Hubei Day," and the "Chu Culture Festival" held in Jingzhou in recent years, transforming embroidery from a commodity into a carrier of cultural diplomacy.

Taking the successful entry of Hainan Li brocade into the Louvre in France as a typical example, this project relied on the resource coordination between the Hainan Provincial Government and the Ministry of Culture and Tourism. Adopting a "ICH + fashion" curatorial approach, a professional team transformed Li brocade patterns into modern aesthetics. With the support of the China-France Cultural Year mechanism and the joint collaboration of diplomatic, cultural, and other departments, it successfully entered a world-class art palace, achieving a leap from a national handicraft to an international fashion symbol. Jingzhou embroidery can learn from this path: the government should take the lead in integrating design, academic, and communication resources, building a promotion model of "national support, professional operation, and international expression," allowing this treasure of Chu culture to truly enter the mainstream Western cultural field and enhance the level of cultural display.

2. Deepen Local Successful Experiences in Cultural and Tourism Digitalization to Build a New Ecosystem for the International Communication of Chu Embroidery

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Policy support should closely follow the trend of digital development, replicate and upgrade Jingzhou's advanced experience in cultural and tourism digitalization. Proactive applications should be made for support such as national cultural digitalization special funds, which can be used to build a "3D Database of Chu Embroidery Patterns" and develop AR experience programs. These should be adapted to international platforms such as TikTok,^[48] transforming static patterns into interactive and communicable digital assets. Efforts should be made to promote documentaries on Chu culture to mainstream domestic and international media. Drawing on the communication strategies of "Dunhuang Digitalization" and the display of Jingzhou Museum's cultural relics on CCTV, the world can be elaborated on the craftsmanship and cultural codes of Chu embroidery through its global broadcasting network. With the power of digitalization, a leap from "cloud tourism in Jingzhou" to "cloud appreciation of Chu embroidery" can be achieved, creating a new immersive international communication ecosystem.

IV. Conclusion

In today's world, ICH work inevitably takes up the task of passing the methods down, fostering the continuation, and making connections across cultures. As one of the most treasured ICH crafts, Jingzhou folk embroidery perfectly demonstrates the vigorous development. Just like the vehicle of cultural and creative exports of Jingzhou folk embroidery with all dimensions integrated and important, it enables us to innovate the communication—this is an essential base for us to get through the unique beauty of Jingzhou embroidery. Broadens out the ways of delivering the information to the audience also helps get into touch with people from all over the globe. Gathering different groups helps gather the energies so that we can pour fresh air into Jingzhou embroidery, bring new points of views to Jingzhou embroidery.

In light of the constantly evolving technological landscape and the growing cultural unity across the world, it is imperative that we continually inform ourselves of foreign culture and customs as well as audience expectations in different countries. Staying abreast of the latest market trends, we need to constantly improve the way we present our cultural goods. Applying a more integrated and creative approach, we would be better able to help the internationalizing Jingzhou folk embroidery industry promote and expand its reach through our new presentations. And doing this well will certainly shed light on important guiding principles (both practice and theory) in assisting those local ICH crafts from other regions who are working towards promoting their craft overseas.

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